

AN AIR-JET COMPACTION SYSTEM FOR DRAPING AND CONSOLIDATION IN THE AUTOMATED MANUFACTURE OF COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY: An automated system was developed for the design and manufacture of fibre reinforced plastic structures to substitute the high cost of labour in the current manual layup processes. This paper discusses a servo-controlled air-jet compaction system, which was designed and manufactured for use as a robot end effector to complete the fifth degree of freedom for an automated manufacturing system to lay-up composite components made from prepreg and dry fabric. This air-jet unit is computer controlled for precise vectorial and spatial positioning with respect to the tool used in the manufacture of a composite component. This enables the unit to be directed normal to the surface of a wide range of geometries of tools. The consolidation of each ply is effected by heated air whose temperature may be varied. The path of the compactor is guided to follow pre-determined computer generated lay-up trajectories, so as to achieve predetermined ply draping.

KEYWORDS: automated manufacture, fibre reinforced plastic composites, robotic end-effector, ply consolidation.

INTRODUCTION

The use of fibre reinforced plastic structure has been limited by their high manufacturing cost due to their labour intensive manual layup processes which are inherently costly and which attract additional costs because of the extensive inspection required for quality control. These issues have been addressed by developing automated flexible manufacturing systems for advanced composite structures. A number of such systems, reported in the open literature, are presently in various stages of development [1 - 4]. A major difficulty identified in all these programs is associated with the consolidation of prepreg and dry fabric tows on the tool, particularly for components with double curvature.

The development of the airjet end-effector for ply consolidation, which is described in this paper is part of larger research program to develop a low cost system for the automated manufacture of high quality composite components from prepreg and dry fabric[5]. This automated layup system uses concurrent design for manufacture in order to simplify the overall process so as to make it more amenable to automated manufacture. The basic system involves generating a draping finite element (FE) model using an FE computer package. The layup in the FE model is defined using a protocol in which the draping sequence of the ply is

defined as part of the design process. The information relating to draping is used to control the automation[5]. The system was designed for cost effective manufacturing by maximising flexibility, minimising human intervention during manufacture and maximising exploitation of a unified computer database.

One of the essential elements of such a system is the process of consolidating each ply into its appropriate position in the tool. An air-jet compactor driven by a servo motor has been developed to use compressed air to consolidate prepeg and tackified dry fabric plies. The orientation of the nozzle at the end of the compactor enables the unit to work on most surface used in creating composite parts, including those with complex curvature..

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Often composite parts involve laying up fabric over curvature that cannot be consolidated using just one roller. Using air to apply the consolidation force enables layup on tools with complex curvature. A part can have some difficult small radius joggles close to complex curved areas and no change in tool will be needed. The air simply conforms to the curvature of the tool. Although the air jet is best suited to parts with complex curvature, it is also able to lay up efficiently onto flat or singly curved tools.

Critical issues

A number of critical issues were considered during the design phase.

1. The unit was required to function in sharp female corners or in small tools where there is limited space. Therefore, the overall size of the airjet end-effector was a critical issue.
2. The control of the nozzle path and velocity was a critical feature. For effective consolidation, it was essential to ensure that, at all phases of the consolidation process, the air-jet was aligned with the normal vectors generated from the CAD process. The starting torque and holding torque required for correct operation needed to be determined at the design stage.
3. The diameters of the high pressure air lines had to be carefully chosen so as to achieve the necessary force to consolidate the plies.
4. Simplicity of construction and operation were major considerations in the design stage.

Force applied

One essential element determining the end effector size was the force applied to the plies, which required a certain diameter of nozzle and channel pressure air. From human hand operating experiments, a force of approximately 20 N[1] was placed on the plies. The pressure obtained from the laboratory compressed air system(Ps) was 700 kPa.

Force required for draping: $F = 20 \text{ N};$
 Pressure obtained from lab system: $P = 700 \text{ kPa};$
 Square of nozzle: $S;$
 Diameter of nozzle: $D;$

$$F = P * S$$

$$S = \pi * (D/2) * (D/2)$$

$$D = 2 * \sqrt{S/\pi} \therefore D = 2 * \sqrt{F/(p*\pi)}$$

$$D = 6 \text{ mm}$$

Therefore, 6 mm inter diameter of nozzle was chosen.

ROTATION

The speed of the nozzle turning had to be compatible with that of the robot's movement so as to complete the movement in approximately the same time or sooner. Calculations were applied for adopting a motor with its gear box and a pair of pulleys as shown in *Figure 1*.

Robot moving speed: $V_r;$
 Nozzle vectorial speed: $V_n;$
 Diameter: $D;$

 Angle rotating speed: $\omega;$
 Nozzle radius: $R_n;$

 Subscripts:
 Nozzle n
 Robot r
 Driving pulley d
 Power pulley p

Figure 1: End effector rotation mechanism

The nozzle vectorial speed (V_n) needs to be similar to the robot arm moving speed (V_r), this was expected in most of applications to be approximately : $V_n = V_r = 1 \text{ m/s}.$

$$V_n = \omega_n * R_n;$$

$$\omega_n = V_n / R_n = V_r / R_n;$$

To avoid the motor hitting the tool but still allow the nozzle to access sharp corners in limited space, a pair of pullies and a belt have been introduced to keep the motor away from rotation wheel.

The pair of pulleys chosen were:

Driving pulley: 40 teeth;

Power pulley: 10 teeth;

$$\omega_p = (R_d / R_p) * \omega_d;$$

$$\therefore \omega_p = (40 / 10) * (1000 / 22.5);$$

$$\omega_p = 177.7 \text{ degrees/sec};$$

$$\therefore \text{Its spinning speed is } 1698 \text{ rotation per minute .}$$

This range of rotation speed from the motor gear box can be adopted to drive the unit.

CONTROL

The control of the unit was performed using software developed to read draping data generated and converted from an FE model. It consisted of two sections:

1. Software to read the draping data and send the command to drive the motor using the converting card.
2. Automated error correcting system.

A servo motor control card was employed to convert the commands to pulses which were increased by a transformer before driving the motor. The motor was then calibrated to identify the number of pulses required to rotate the nozzle one degree while the compressed air was being ejected.

Since a small amount of error occurs during the process of position movement each time, a feed back system was necessary. It helped correct the error in order to obtain the precise draping position. The motor used allowed the addition of the feedback so as to produce a servo motor. A potentiometer installed in the servo generate the voltage signal which was sent back to the servo motor controller. This then terminated the motor rotation after the feedback signal matched the pulse signal sent from computer.

OVERALL AIR-JET COMPACTOR UNIT

The overall control system schematic is depicted in *figure 2*. The diagram of the air-jet compactor unit is presented in *figure 3*. These include three parts: Movement mechanism, Air-jetting and Control of motion and jet.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the air compaction control system

The reason for installing the transmission inside the tube, that supports the wheel and is held by robot, come about for two main reasons. First, it could reduce the overall size of the unit, enabling the unit to work in small space. Second, it contributes to safety considerations.

Figure 3: Diagram of air-jet end effector

Moving parts

The nozzle at the end of the wheel is driven by the motor via pulleys and a belt, after the speed had been reduced and torque had been increased by a gear box at end of the motor. It can rotate up to 100 degrees on each side, which ensures the nozzle is able to point normal to any curved surface when used with a vertical rotational axis from robot. All moving parts were kept small to ensure the final end effector was able to access small radius and parts with deep sections. Further reduction in size was impractical as a certain airflow was needed using standard airline thus dictating the size of the overall dimensions used.

Air-jetting parts

After the command was given by the software the compressed air was turned on by a solenoid switch and the air was ejected out from nozzle by passing through a pipe situated internally to the rotating cylinder the nozzle was attached to.

Controlling parts

Following the given computer command, a servo motor controller received the pulse sent from a computer control card. This pulse was then increased to allow it to drive the motor step to its position. The potentiometer at the end of gear box generated the feed back voltage from the motor rotation back to the controller so as to modify the nozzle to the correct position.

TEST OF CONCEPT

Calibration of the nozzle controller was performed by finding what pulse corresponded to what angle. This following relationship was found;

$$\text{Pulses} = 21/9 \times \text{Angle (in degrees)}$$

The unit has been fully calibrated and basic tests performed using the system software. However, final testing of the end effector will require the integration of all hardware and control by the software in order for it to be fully tested..

The draping force, although enough to consolidate ply onto simple curved tools, would not be adequate for shape corners. These, however, could be consolidated by introducing an air pressure increaser (pneumatic air ejector) in the air line. Heating the compressed air would also help press the plies into sharp corners, as a result of the prepreg softening tack increasing. Dry fabric with binder (B staged resin) could also be influenced by such heating. The air heating system is being developed.

CONCLUSION

An air-jet compactor unit has been designed for use in an automated composite manufacture layup cell which enables plies to be layed onto various types of complex curved tooling.

A prototype airjet compactor has been constructed, calibrated and its operational aspects successfully tested.

The control system required to operate the compactor has been designed, constructed and successfully tested.

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